
79. More insights into non-single stars

IN MY PREVIOUS ESSAY (#78, 27 June) I looked at just two of the papers on results from Gaia DR3 (released on 13 June 2022), and focused on the impact that Gaia is now having on the astrometric discovery of exoplanets.

These early results are emerging from the collective work of just one of the three sub-groups of ‘Coordination Unit 4’. As I noted there, CU4 handles the downstream treatment of sources which demand a very different astrometric analysis compared to that of otherwise ‘normal’ stars in our Galaxy and beyond, specifically for non-single stars, solar system objects, and galaxies.

By focusing on those first results on exoplanets, I was picking out just a part of the work of this CU4 subgroup, and its comprehensive treatment of non-single stars. Here, I’ll look at some other results.

FIRST, LET ME PROVIDE the context to this essay, by repeating what I noted in essay #78. Over the past century, binary (and multiple) star systems have been discovered through a variety of methods, and they can be loosely classified as *visual* binaries (where both components are ‘visible’), *astrometric* (where the companion’s presence is revealed by the photocentric motion), *spectroscopic* (revealed as orbital variations of spectral lines), or *eclipsing* (where the light from one component is eclipsed by the orbital motion of the other).

With its combination of unprecedented astrometric and photometric accuracy, Gaia is in a position both to discover, and to characterise, most of these types, simultaneously and uniformly, and in substantial numbers.

INDEED, in their overall treatment of non-single stars, a whole host of other interesting results are starting to emerge. In this essay, I’ll pick out a few of these described in the recent (DR3) paper on the non-single star results by Arenou et al. (2022): specifically considering stellar masses, brown dwarf companions, compact companions, and ellipsoidal and other variations.

Most of these topics really merit much more space, and I’ll undoubtedly return to some of them in more detail in the future. Meanwhile, this is a taster!

STELLAR MASSES: Given their fundamental role in models of stellar structure and evolution, it may seem surprising that accurate masses are known for only around a hundred stars, a situation that has advanced only modestly since the review by Andersen (1991).

This is because a star’s mass can only be directly determined from the orbital motion of a binary system. Total system masses, $M_1 + M_2$, can be estimated when the period (P) and linear semi-major axis (a) of an orbital binary are known. Accurate total ($M_1 + M_2$) masses are therefore known for many systems, although the cubic dependency on a implies that errors are very sensitive both to parallax error, and to errors on a and P .

Individual stellar masses, in contrast, can only be measured under special circumstances, specifically for double-lined spectroscopic binaries (SB2 systems), and only by combining the spectroscopic orbit with that from astrometry. This is because astrometry describes motion on the *plane* of the sky (with the 7 classical orbit elements being $P, a'', e, i, \omega, \Omega, T_0$). Spectroscopy describes motion *along* the line-of-sight (with the conventional spectroscopic elements for a double-lined SB2 spectroscopic binary being $P, \gamma, K_1, K_2, e, \omega, T_0$).

Without delving into the precise meaning of these quantities, it turns out that four are in common between the two solutions (P, e, ω, T_0), such that the combination of observations can yield individual component masses. In the case of single-lined (SB1) systems, the mass of the primary has to be assumed (generally inferred from the spectral type). In the case of double-lined spectroscopic binaries (SB2) the mass ratio (M_1/M_2) is determined, and individual masses result from knowledge of the orbit inclination, i , provided by astrometry.

From the Gaia data alone, combining the available astrometric and SB2 orbits presently yields about 70 component masses (Arenou et al. 2022; Table 3). Many more will become available when the Gaia astrometry is combined with external catalogues of spectroscopic binaries (e.g. the 8105 SB2 systems from APOGEE DR17). Something similar was done for seven SB2 binaries in the Hipparcos catalogue (Arenou et al. 2000).

BROWN DWARF COMPANIONS: Due to the large ‘reflex’ motion induced in their host stars, early radial velocity surveys were expected to discover brown dwarf companions to solar-type stars with relative ease, and in reasonable numbers. Their masses and orbit sizes would provide important constraints on theories of formation and evolution of brown dwarfs (and planets).

But a feature of early radial velocity exoplanet surveys was the paucity of close-in ($a < 3 - 4$ au) sub-stellar objects with masses of $10 - 80M_J$, known as the *brown dwarf desert* (Marcy & Butler, 2000). Subsequent radial velocity surveys of several thousand stars have confirmed this pattern, finding brown dwarf companions out to $P \sim 10$ yr, but with few in the mass and separation range characterising the ‘desert’. Pre-Gaia, only some 100 brown dwarfs were known around F, G, or K stars.

Meanwhile, detailed models constructed before the release of DR3 predicted that Gaia should discover some 30–50 000 brown dwarfs from the astrometric (orbital) perturbations of their host stars (Holl et al. 2022).

Already, from Gaia DR3, Arenou et al. (2022) report 1843 brown dwarf *candidates*, of which only 10 were previously known from ground-based radial velocity surveys. Under various assumptions, these first results indicate, for example, that the frequency of brown dwarfs around M dwarfs with $P < 1000$ days is about 0.3%.

COMPACT COMPANIONS: A host star’s orbital motion, ‘tugged’ upon by an orbiting body, does not depend on the orbiting body being visible. This opens the possibility of detecting any sort of body orbiting a star, whether it is visible (another star), of low luminosity (a brown dwarf, white dwarf, or a planet), or any other form of more ‘exotic’ compact object, such as a neutron star or even a black hole. Indeed, the astrometric orbits of non-single stars in Gaia DR3 are giving the first hints about the existence of all of these various classes of object.

Identification of a compact low-luminosity companion in general depends both on the *mass ratio* of the two components, but also on their *luminosity* ratio, together characterised by what Arenou et al. (2022) describe as their ‘astrometric mass ratio function’.

Their histogram of companion masses for more than 700 compact object candidates (their Figure 36) suggests that most of these companions are white dwarfs, with a clear narrow peak at around 0.6 solar masses, as for field white dwarfs. They estimate that Gaia should increase the number of known binary systems with white dwarf components by at least a factor 10.

More exotic still, SB1 sources with a large mass function could point to stars with a neutron star or even black hole companion. It is too early to draw clear conclusions, although they hint that HIP 15429 (amongst others) may be a B5 Ib star with an orbiting black hole, although it may instead be an Algol-type or triple system.

JUST AS NASA’S Kepler satellite revealed many new astrophysical phenomena by virtue of its accurate high-cadence photometry of a very large number of stars, so Gaia is poised to capitalise on its simultaneous combination of high-accuracy astrometry, multi-epoch photometry and, for the brightest stars, radial velocities. I will give four examples of such capabilities.

First, and perhaps most easily appreciated, it is not always straightforward to distinguish a single-lined spectroscopic binary (SB1) from a long-period variable, i.e. to distinguish orbit-induced radial velocity variations from (single star) radial pulsations. Gaia offers new prospects to disentangle the two effects, and various examples are given in Arenou et al. (2022; Table 6).

A second example are the ‘ellipsoidal variables’, close binary stars whose components are physically distorted by their mutual gravitation, but with orbit inclinations too small to create eclipses (such stars are not exactly ellipsoidal in shape but, rather, fill their Roche equipotential surfaces). Resulting light curves, due to the changing projected areas and surface brightnesses of the distorted stars, typically show periodic variability, albeit with amplitudes of only a few per cent at most.

Such ellipsoidal variabilities have also become of interest in exoplanet studies, and in particular based on Kepler photometry, where they were first seen in the bright system HAT-P-7 b, in which a transiting ‘hot Jupiter’ (of $1.7M_J$) orbits an F6 star with $a = 4R_\star$.

Again, Arenou et al. (2022; Table 6) give several examples (including V1540 Cyg) where the preliminary classification as a long-period variable is re-classified as an ellipsoidal variable by noting that the variability period is exactly one half that of its astrometric orbit. Similarly, sources for which the two periods are in good agreement generally point to true pulsating stars.

My third example is a class of sources which show a significant (and arbitrary) phase lag between the two periods. This may be revealing binary systems in which the light variation is due to star spots on the primary star, modulated in a spin-orbit synchronised binary system.

Finally, EL CVn systems are short-period eclipsing binaries consisting of an A/F primary and a low-mass pre-He white dwarf secondary. As a rare (brief) stage of binary evolution, they result from mass transfer from the pre-HeWD progenitor to the brighter primary star.

For the known 9.5 mag system HD 23692, the combined Gaia epoch photometry and radial velocity curves (their Figure 28) show that the deeper eclipse actually corresponds to the secondary component (a characteristic of such systems). And the secondary eclipse in G_{BP} is much deeper than that in G_{RP} , providing further confirmation of the higher temperature of the secondary.

G AIA’S NON-SINGLE STARS really are providing a spectacular haul of new astronomical insights!